

Increasing maize productivity in Meranti Coastal Land through applying biological fertilizers

*Ida Nur Istina**, Rahmiwati Yusuf, Sri Swastika
Riau Assessment Institutes for Agricultural Technology,
Kaharudin Nst. streets 341 Pekanbaru Riau Indonesia
*Corresponding author: idanuristina@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Coastal land is a suboptimal land which is potentially developed for supporting food availability in the future. Indonesian Coastal land area covers 20.1 million hectares, 6 million ha of which are potential for crops. The high salinity that constrains agricultural development can be minimized by applying the appropriate technology such as varieties that tolerance to salinity, and application of manure and bio-fertilizer that containing the potential microbes to improve plant resistance to environmental stress. This study aimed to obtain information of maize adaptable varieties and fertilization to improve maize productivity in coastal land. The study was conducted at Meranti Coastal Land in 2017 using the randomized block design with 4 treatments and 5 replications. Varieties of maize used were Bisma, Bima 9, Bima 19 URI and Bisi 2. To increase the land productivity, cow manure and cow manure + biological fertilizer with containing nitrogen fixing and phosphate solubilizing microbe were applied. The results showed that the enrichment of biological fertilizer can improve the performance and yield of maize in coastal land that exposed to salt. Variety of Bisi 2 showed high adaptation to environmental stress followed by Bima 19 URI, Bisma and Bima 9.

Keywords: *maize, coastal land, biological fertilizer, productivity improvement*

INTRODUCTION

The high land conversion encourages infertile land including coastal land to be used as agricultural land with the need for adaptive and feasible technology. The area of coastal land in Indonesia covers 20.1 million hectares, which has the potential as a huge environmental resource and service but has not been yet utilized (Lasabuda, 2013). About 6 million hectares of total areas have potentially been developed food crops. According to Alihamsyah (2004), tidal lands are distributed 7.147 million ha in Sumatra, 5.939 million ha in Kalimantan, 6.415 million ha in Papua, 371 thousand ha in Sulawesi, and 237 thousand ha in Maluku and Nusa Tenggara. The coastal lands are potentially developed for agriculture and fisheries (Widuri et al., 2015), both food crops and horticultural crops (Maroeto and Sasongko, 2004). It is further mentioned

that the successful farming in coastal land is determined by success in managing natural constraints.

Coastal lands are non-productive land for agriculture. They contain peat, clay or sandy soil. The three types of soil require different handling techniques due to different physical, chemical and biological aspects of the soil. Physically the sandy coastal land has poor properties such as lack of water holding capacity, coarse structure, granules and not compact. Coarse coastal land cause dry fast due to rapid water depletion. Chemically the coastal land has a high salts accumulation, soil cation exchange capacity (CEC) is very low because of no colloidal soil and zero surface charges, so that they do not retain nutrients. In terms of soil biology, activity of soil microorganisms are limited and soil organic matter is very low, they can break down complex compounds into simpler compounds in the soil so it can be beneficial to plants. This is in line with Boga (2017) states that the problems of agricultural development in the coastal area of Riau is a high acidity level, high salinity, and Fe toxicity. This condition causes the growth of roots, stems and leaf is reduced due to metabolic imbalance caused by poisoning ions $\text{Na}^+ + \text{Cl}^-$, osmotic stress, and nutrient deficiency (Sembiring and Gani, 2007). The presence of sea water intrusion into the farming areas as a result of the reduced number of planting mangrove cause land becomes saline. Krisnawati and Adie (2009) state that salinity occurs due to global climate change which has an impact on rising sea levels, and generally spread in saline land at coastal areas, irrigated land, excess fertilized land and naturally saline land.

In Indonesia, there is an area of 0.4 million ha of saline, and is expected to increase along with rising sea levels due to global warming. The characteristics of saline soil are $\text{pH} < 8.5$, and are dominated by salts of Na, Ca, and Mg in the form of chloride and sulfate which cause low availability of N, P, Mn, Cu, Zn, and Fe in soil, high osmotic pressure, the weakness of the movement of water and air, and low activity of soil microbes. Salinity causes morphological, physiological, biochemical, and anatomical changes (Tester and Davenport, 2003). According to Sudrajat (2013), problems of soil physical and chemical in developing coastal land also experience social problems such as many isolated communities and polarization of social (rural two classes).

Various obstacles in coastal land can be overcome with technology, such as: planting saline and/or acid resistant varieties, soil improvement, water management arrangements, fertilization, cropping arrangements, and proper planting calendars. Edi (2010) stated that mitigation and adaptation can be done through a variety of ways, including the manufacture of safe beds from water ponds for roots, the selection of amendments that can reduce soil salinity, the selection of plants that resist drought and inundation, and cropping rotation patterns.

Corn is one of the agricultural commodities that play a role in realizing national food security, which is used both as food raw materials, liquid sugar industry, and animal feed industry. National maize production is currently still not meeting the needs, so the expansion of the area through various programs is carried out not only on potential land but also towards sub-optimal land such as coastal land. Efforts to increase productivity are also carried out through genetic engineering carried out by the Research Institute. Until now, maize with high levels of drought-resistant productivity is available such as a hybrid corn of Bima 4, and a composite corn of Lamuru with potential yield of 11.71 and 7.6 tons / ha, respectively Besides that, it presents early maturing corn varieties such as Bima 7, Bima 8 and Gumarang with a harvesting age of 89; 88 and 82 days after planting, respectively. Corn varieties that are resistant to puddles are now engineered and obtained 5 strains with a potential yield of 8-9 tons / ha namely GM 226, GM 228, GM 291, GM 327, and GM 338 (Balitbangtan, 2011). Considering the importance of food security, it is necessary to study to get technology to increase corn productivity in saline land a colorless, transparent, odorless, tasteless liquid that forms the seas, lakes, rivers, and rain and is the basis of the fluids of living organisms.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The research was conducted at Segomeng Meranti district Riau Province using the randomized block design with 4 treatments and 5 replications. Varieties of maize that tolerance in drought and pool used were Bisma, Bima 9, Bima 19 URI and Bisi 2. To increase the productivity of land applied cow manure and cow manure + biological fertilizer with containing nitrogen fixing and phosphate solubilizing microbe. Planting is use to legowo planting system, with a planting distance of 75 x 50 cm and 2 seeds per planting hole. The parameters observations were vegetative and generative growth. The collected data was tabulated and analyzed

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Plant Agronomic Performance

Based on field observations, corn cultivation up to 60 days after planting showed good performance where the averaged plant height of Bisma, Bima 9, Bima 19 and Bisi 2 were 191.4 cm; 185.0 cm; 189.4 cm and 190.4 cm, respectively. Bisma as composite maize variety showed the highest averaged plant height compared to others. Suspected to be related to the plant where for growth it does not require high nutrient adequacy as hybrid corn compared to not

significantly different from Bisi 2 varieties which are considered adaptive against environmental stress.

The addition of organic fertilizers to anticipate the salinity stress showed a positive impact on plant vegetative growth shown by the response of plant height increment and number of leaves as presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Maize Plant Height (cm) in 60 days old (left); Maize Leave Number on Various Fertilizer (right)

The application of manure can increase plant height, number of leaves and number of cobs in a row as much as 4%, 1.58%, and 4%, respectively while the application of a combination of manure and biological fertilizer can increase 7%, 2.14%, 10%, respectively compared to controls.

Variety of Bisma, Bima 9 and Bima 19 showed a positive response to the addition of organic matter, while Bisi 2 was not significantly increased by manure although with the addition of manure and biological fertilizer increased real. This indicates that the use of manure in addition to improving soil nutrients is also able to stimulate stress caused by salinity as well as biological fertilizers, especially in Bisma varieties.

The amount of tuna produced by the Bisma variety is on average 1 piece, while the Bima 9 and Bima 10 varieties vary. In the Bisi 2 variety, it produces an average of 2 cobs. As presented in Fig. 2, application of manure can increase the number of cobs except in Bisi 2 which increases with the addition of manure and bio fertilizers. This indicates that manure alone does not meet the need for metabolic processes to increase the amount of cob.

Figure 2. The maize cob number on various fertilizer (left) and the effect of organic material on maize generative performance at coastal land (right)

In the weight parameters of cobs, age 60 days after planting, it can be seen that the varieties determine the weight of mackerel, where the Bisma variety gives the highest ear weight compared to other varieties. Bisi 2 and the lowest followed Bima 9. The addition of organic matter showed a trend of positive response to the parameter corn crop yield in coastal lands.

This indicates that the addition of organic matter origin manure and biological fertilizers containing macro and micro nutrients and soil microbes were able to improve soil structure and reduce the impact of stress and increase the yield of corn in coastal land.

Figure 3. The maize performance at generative phase

Yield

The presence of rat attacks resulted in the harvest of corn at an appropriate age. The results of the field observations indicate that corn yields the highest average was obtained from varieties Bisi 2 (13,3 t ha⁻¹) followed Bima 19 (7,46 t ha⁻¹), Bisma (7.3 t ha⁻¹), and the lowest in Bhima 9 (6.8 t ha⁻¹). It's indicate that Bisi 2 is resistant to salinity stress on the coastal land of Meranti Re gency. Furthermore with the addition of organic material can be in the know that the addition of organic matter in maize in coastal lands were able to increase corn production

Figure 4. The effect of fertilizer application on maize Production at Meranti Coastal land

Based on the results of analysis showed that the fertilizer application cow manure and the combination of manure and biological fertilizers containing functional microbial markedly increase the production of corn in the coastal area. The increase of corn productivity due to manure application and its combination with biological fertilizers is 45.1 and 77.3% (Bisma), 21.7 and 65.6% (Bima 9), 16.5 and 71.6% (Bima 19), 24.8 and 24.8% (Bisi 2), respectively compared to control. This indicates that manure containing organic ingredients is capable to improve the rooting media conditions so that the plant roots can more easily absorb the nutrients. While the addition of microbial biofertilizers containing potentially allow microbes can work in providing essential nutrients besides the decomposition process does for subsistence causing more land suitable for plant development. Field reality also shows that the response of Bisi 2 is not significantly different from bio fertilizers. This is likely due to the nature of hybrid plants that respond to nutrient intake in large quantities.

CONCLUSIONS

- Bisi 2 Corn Varieties are quite adaptive to land with saline exposure followed by Bima 19 URI; Bisma and Bima 9
- The use of organic materials can increase corn production on coastal land

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research activity was funded by national core budget from the Ministry of Agriculture through Riau AIATs. We would like thank to Damri Maulana for his helpfully.

REFERENCES

- Alihamsyah.T. 2004. Potensi dan Pendayagunaan Lahan Rawa untuk Peningkatan Produksi Padi. Ekonomi Padi dan Beras Indonesia. Dalam Faisal kasrino, Effendi Pasandaran, dn AM. Fagi (Penyunting) Badan Litbang Pertanian, Jakarta.
- Boga, A.K. 2017. Lahan Bergaram di Pesisir Bisa Ditanami, Riau Bisa Surplus Beras. *Detik Finance.Com*. Rabu, 27 Desember 2017 13:28 WIB
- Badan Litbang Pertanian, 2011. Teknologi Tanaman Pangan Menghadapi Perubahan Iklim. www.litbang.pertanian.go.id/berita/one/971
- Dachlan A., Nurlina Kasim dan A. Kurnia Sari. 2013. Uji Ketahanan Salinitas Beberapa Varietas Jagung (*Zea mays L.*) Dengan Menggunakan Agen

Seleksi NaCl. *Jurnal Biogenesis*. ISSN 2302-1616 Vol 1, No. 1, Juni 2013, hal 9-17

- Edi, S.P. 2010. Dampak Mitigasi Dan Adaptasi Perubahan Iklim Pada Areal Lahan Pertanian Pesisir Pantai. <http://kmi-web23.open.ac.uk:8081/display/12218370>. [Diunduh 26 Mei 2015]
- Krisnawati, A. dan M.M. Adie. 2009. Kendali Genetik Dan Karakter Penentu Toleransi Kedelai Terhadap Salinitas. *Iptek Tanaman Pangan* 4(2): 222-237.
- Lasabuda, R. 2013. Regional Development In Coastal and Ocean in Archipelago Perspective of the Republic Of Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmiah Platax*. I (2): 92-101.
- Maroeto dan P.E. Sasongko. 2004. Alternatif Pemilihan Tanaman Pangan Pada Lahan Pesisir Dengan Pendekatan Evaluasi Tingkat Kesesuaian Lahan Di Daerah Kabupaten Sidoarjo. *Jurnal Penelitian Ilmu-ilmu Pertanian* 4(1): 30-40.
- Sembiring, H. dan A. Gani. 2006. Adaptasi Varietas Padi Pada Tanah Terkena Tsunami. http://www.dpi.nsw.gov.au/data/assets/pdf_file/0009/199449/Adaptability-of-rice-on-tsunami-affected-soil.pdf. [Diakses tanggal 17 Mei 2008].
- Sudrajat, J. 2013. Potency and Problems Of Coastal Region Development In West Borneo. *Journal Social Economic of Agriculture* 2(1): 29-41. <https://media.neliti.com/.../23024-ID-potency-and-problems-of-coa>
- Tester, M. and R. Davenport. 2003. Na Tolerance and Na Transport in Higher Plants. *Annals Botany* 91:503- 527.
- Widuri, L.I., D. Wulanjari, A. Widayanti, S. Angraini, A.F. Prabowo, R. Respati, F. Prasetyo, H.D. Prabakti, and M. Kurdiantoro. 2015. The Study Of Agroecosystem Potency And Management On Coastal Area: A Case In Watu Ulo Beach, Jember Regency, East Java. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Lahan Suboptimal, Palembang 8-9 Oktober 2015 ISBN: 979-587-580-9. <https://pur-plso.unsri.ac.id/.../45Laily-Widuri-Kajian-Potensi-Agroekosistem-dan-Pengelolaan>